

Why (mathematics) education in a democracy must be critical education

Daniela Steflitsch, University of Klagenfurt, daniela.steflitsch@aau.at

Education, as a fixed component of society, has the task of forming democratic principles and values in addition to subject-specific goals. Critical competencies must be promoted in every school subject. In this paper, teaching principles of critical education are derived from the requirements of democracy. Furthermore, it is argued that mathematics education has a special role to play here, but that, at the same time, mathematics' unique characteristics may explain why it is still no matter of course to integrate critical aspects into this subject.

Introduction

What is the main purpose of education? What do we, as educators, want our students to learn? What skills do we want them to acquire? These questions are by no means easy to answer and have triggered debates in various disciplines. If you look at these questions with Klafki's (2007) understanding of education, one reason for the recurring debates about the goals of education might be the ever-changing demands on the educational system as our societies are exposed to constant change: 'education issues are social issues' (p. 49, own translation). He did not want to claim that the educational system must be oriented to the basic structures of society but that education systems as an integrated part of society have the opportunity and the task of assessing and helping to shape social developments. In this sense, education is a fixed component of society, and at the same time, society is a fixed component of education. On this background, we should dare a closer look at the interplay of (mathematics) education and society at a general level.

Most Western societies are built on democratic structures and values. However, the concept of democracy is multidimensional and cannot be easily explained. The large number of different definitions and descriptions of democracy suggests that it is by no means a fixed construct but rather a fundamental form of coexistence that follows certain basic ideas and values. Aguilar and Zavaleta (2012) tried to analyze and sum up different interpretations of the concept of democracy, which were used in journals for mathematics education. They identified that democracy not only has a political (free elections), a juridical (equal rights), and an economic (distribution of cultural and natural goods) dimension but, most importantly, a socio-cultural one. Other definitions highlight this aspect of democracy as well: Democracy is also characterized by creating conditions for the development of human dignity, equal opportunities, and emancipation, including that different ways of thinking and different

Please cite as: Steflitsch, D. (2021). Why (mathematics) education in a democracy must be critical education. In D. Kollosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 3, pp. 967–976. Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5416634>

opinions are not just tolerated but welcomed. This means that democracy thrives on the citizens' individual contributions and that everyone can and should contribute to a functional democracy. This already points to the fact that a democracy is always in kind of a process and not a fixed condition. West (2005) described it with reference to the use of the word – for him, democracy is 'more a verb than a noun' (p. 68), as this would better describe the process in which a democracy constantly finds itself. A democratic society must, therefore, continuously work to remain one, since it will always have to face new challenges – be it through processes of globalization, immigration, or budding ideologies that are represented by political extremists.

But how can we best ensure to develop our society in a democratic manner for a better living in the future for all citizens? How can we prepare our youth to get involved in the development process in the best possible way and thus help shape their future? How can we accomplish that they are becoming active citizens that can make decisions after thoroughly weighing up all options and then taking responsibility for them? As the former secretary-general of the United Nations Kofi Annan stated in a speech at a world conference in 1998: 'No one is born a good citizen; no nation is born a democracy. Rather both are processes that continue to evolve over a lifetime. Young people must be included from birth.' Education, therefore, plays an essential role. Dewey (1916/1997) was one of the advocates who already insisted at the beginning of the 20th century that a democratic society can never function without an educated citizenry. People need to be informed to participate intelligently within private or political life. The question remains how such education has to look like if it is to meet these requirements.

Dewey and others criticized education systems that do not in some way work for the purpose of maintaining democracy, but mainly to attract the best-trained workers in order to be and remain economically competitive and to position themselves in the international market. In the same manner, Giroux and McLaren (1989) argued that it is not enough that schools only provide skills and knowledge that are necessary for successfully competing in the world market. With this kind of education, the system is producing workers instead of citizens.

Another criticized mode of education is when schools are considered a place where knowledge is simply transferred into the students' heads and where students should simply remember the pre-structured and presented information. Already at the beginning of the 20th century, the German educator Kühnel (1916/1950) criticized that the (teaching) goals in school are always material in nature, that everything revolves around the teaching of this material, and that the entire demand on school is governed by it. Thus, school makes its students dependent – 'dependent in judgment, dependent in feeling, dependent in decisions and also in action – [...] it makes the students wait [...] for the stimulus to do something' (Kühnel, 1924, p. 96, own translation). Freire (1970/2014) called this kind of education the 'banking' concept. He described it as an educational concept where 'knowledge is a gift bestowed by those who consider themselves knowledgeable upon those whom they consider to know nothing' (p. 72). How should students learn to actively participate in society if they

Why (mathematics) education in a democracy must be critical education

are trained to be passive by listening instead of participating, receiving pre-structured information without thinking for themselves? Hytten (2008) stated that despite the fact that, as mentioned above, democracy is in a state of constant change, it 'is taught as if it is a fixed, static system passed on to younger generations' (p. 337). She indicated that the school system – as it is – teaches students that 'right answers are rewarded far more than good questions, critical thought, imagination, or creativity' (p. 339). Such an approach of imparting knowledge can never meet the requirements to turn students into responsible citizens who can actively participate in society and critically reflect on the decisions made by our representatives. We cannot expect our students to develop democratic values if an authoritarian style is used in class. That already indicates how closely education is linked to social systems and that they cannot be considered separately.

If we genuinely perceive students as citizens-in-the-making and not as future workers or objects to be fed with pre-structured knowledge that should only be trained to give 'right' answers, then, I will argue, *education in a democracy can be nothing other than critical education*. I start out with what can be understood under critical education and elaborate on the principles that should be fulfilled in such a type of education and on how these contribute to educate democratic citizens and to counteract non-democratic educational principles. I then turn to the point that mathematics education has a special role within this debate and why it might be particularly difficult to bring a critical aspect into this subject. Moreover, this demand seems to be more crucial than ever, considering the new challenges to a democracy that our fast-moving and globalized times bring with them, which I will discuss in more detail thereafter.

Being critical in education

At first, it would be necessary to clarify what can be understood by the word *critical* and how we can understand it in connection to education. A glance at the Oxford Dictionary (Oxford University Press, 2020) reveals five different meanings. First of all, it defines being critical as 'expressing disapproval'. This meaning of the word usually has a rather negative connotation. In connection with education, this definition would fall short and would degrade education and school to a nagger about social processes. The description of 'critical' in the context of education, which seems to be the most relevant one, is only found in fourth place in the dictionary.¹ Here, being critical also means 'making careful judgments' – 'involving making fair, careful judgments about the good and bad qualities of someone or something'. The use of the term also depends on the historical background the word might carry. The concept of critique appears very prominently in Kant's *Critique of Pure Reason*, where he attempted to bring together rationalism and empiricism through his critical philosophical reflection. In doing so, he attributed great importance to the use of reason,

¹ The second, third, and fifth definition of the word seems to be less relevant in the school context. Further definitions of the word "critical" within Oxford dictionary: 'important', 'serious/dangerous', 'of art/music/books etc.'

which, according to him, includes the ability to draw conclusions and to examine oneself. The term was interpreted differently when it appeared within *critical theory*, where the meaning is understood as a further development of Marxist theory that focuses primarily on social aspects and aims at exposing its mechanisms of domination and oppression and questioning its ideologies. In the context of education in a democracy, the latter interpretation seems to form a good basis, although I would argue that at least some aspects of Kant's perception of critique would fit within a critical education as well.

The critical education approach evolved from various theoretical concepts like critical theory, with its representatives of the Frankfurt School like Horkheimer, Adorno, and Habermas, or *critical pedagogy* with theorists like Freire, Giroux, and Klafki. There is no general definition of the concept. I understand critical education as an education that enables students to critically examine aspects that surround them (whether private or societal). For that purpose, they should be able to understand the background of these circumstances, identify relevant information as such, recognize the possible (possibly veiled) interests of the involved actors, place the situation in a larger context, and argue how they draw their well-founded conclusions after comparing them with possible other ones. They are then capable of taking responsibility for their decisions derived from their conclusions, and these should, if necessary, lead them to take action. This makes critical education an active education rather than a passive one.

Following the definition and derived from the above requirements for maintaining a democratic society, certain guiding principles need to be followed to genuinely foster critical education. I will argue how these principles meet the demanded requirements of education in a democratic manner and counteract the other forms of education (that are criticized).

Content-related principles

Including relevant extra-school contexts. If school functions as an integrated part of society and vice versa, it must not act as a kind of parallel world in which no reference is made to real-life beyond school. Rather, it must directly include current or past social events and developments in everyday teaching. First of all, this also ensures that the school keeps track of important societal developments and does not just fulfill its mission to prepare students for their future jobs. As Dewey (1997) already pointed out:

There is the standing danger that the material of formal instruction will be merely the subject matter of the schools, isolated from the subject matter of life-experience. [...] When the acquiring of information [...] do[es] not influence the formation of a social disposition, ordinary vital experience fails to gain in meaning, while schooling, in so far, creates only 'sharps' in learning—that is, egoistic specialists. (p. 13)

Students should thus gain a general understanding of societal processes, including different ways of looking at them, as they are dealt with in different school subjects. This should enable them to better recognize the relations between these societal topics.

Critically reflecting on school subject matter. It is just as necessary to talk about and critically reflect on the subject matter of the schools too, as they are always value-loaded. As

Why (mathematics) education in a democracy must be critical education

Skovsmose (1985) summed it up, students need to develop a ‘critical distance’ towards content taught in school. Teachers should include discussions about interests or assumptions, as well as about the limits of a subject, into class. Otherwise, it can easily happen that things are taught as if they were the only ‘right’ thing leaving no space for other perspectives – which makes one think more of methods of dictatorship than of a democracy. If an educational practice is to make students only listen and remember, they will not be able (or would not feel the urge) to question the information imparted when a teacher introduces new knowledge. In that case, they would just as well accept wrong as right. Kühnel (1950) already pointed out that ‘the mechanical word memory is completely non-judgmental at first. [...] A child learns right and wrong just as easily’ (p. 141, own translation).

As education is supposed to be so much more than the mere teaching of subject matter, evolving a critical gaze on curriculum contents as well as on contents evolving extra-curricular, seems to form a major principle of it and of preparing the democratic citizen.

Learning-environment related principles

Dialogical teacher-student relationship. In addition to the content, it is essential *how* this content is conveyed. Within critical education, the teacher-student communication should not be one-sided (teacher reports and explains to the students), but students’ contributions and opinions should be included in the lessons. This may require a rethinking of the teacher’s role, as within such a pedagogy, ‘the teacher is no longer merely the-one-who-teaches, but one who is himself taught in dialogue with the students, who in turn while being taught also teach. They become jointly responsible for a process in which all grow’ (Freire, 1970/2014, p. 80). Therefore, lessons need to be carried out more in a form of dialogue, where students are also welcomed to integrate their former experiences into the learning processes. In this way, students are somehow involved in designing the educational process. They learn early that individual contributions are important, that their questions and points of view are taken seriously, and thus also begin to take responsibility for their own learning process.

Focusing on the process, not only on results. As becoming critical is not a competence that can simply be passed on by mere information, students must practice it themselves in different situations. Therefore, the classroom atmosphere should be designed to allow for an open, critical exchange on in- as well as on out-of-school topics. Questions and opposing views should be dealt with openly and perceived as enrichment in everybody’s learning process. Critical reasoning, even if not always successful, should get far more rewarded than quickly getting solutions without knowing why these are considered the right ones. The focus is thus on *how* and *why* a solution comes about rather than the solution itself.

Practicing democratic principles. Pluralism, as a guiding principle in democratic societies, values citizens in their diversity and does not limit their opinions. A democracy allows for different attitudes, views, interests, or beliefs – indeed, it thrives on them. Therefore, the opportunity to openly exchange and discuss ideas and former experiences in an educational environment not only makes school more relevant to students, but allows them to practice important democratic principles. They learn to tolerate other opinions from their classmates,

which possibly leads them to rethink their own points of view. At the same time, they acquire argumentative skills when they justify their standpoint and defend it against others. Thus, this kind of learning environment might lead to the activation of various thought and reflection processes. In such a way of conceiving education, the classroom becomes a place where the learning process is collectively managed and driven forward, by bringing in a variety of opinions and bringing reasoned arguments for and against them: where students realize that their voices count and thus step out of their passive roles as mere listeners, where they are encouraged to actively participate in class, and where they can take responsibility for their own learning process as they realize that participation can bring about change (even if only on a small scale).²

Therefore, following these principles might form a fundamental basis for educating critical democratic citizens. However, it is also clear that the concept of critical education can only fulfill its purpose holistically if these principles are incorporated into all school subjects. In doing so, no subject should be allowed to evade its responsibility. Otherwise, it quickly appears as if there are subjects that either have nothing to contribute to the development of a critical competence (begging the question of these subjects then still have any justification at all in this understanding of education) or as if there are subjects where one does not need critical competences at all. Some have already pointed out the enormous importance of mathematics for the education of critical citizens since numbers play an essential role in political debates and other social issues and are often used to legitimize decisions. Moreover, the use of mathematics might even create realities.

Being critical in mathematics education

The pioneers in this respect were Skovsmose and Frankenstein, who quite simultaneously – in the mid-1980s – developed a concept of *critical mathematics education* (CME). Skovsmose (1994) drew our attention to the *formatting power* of mathematics, as realities can be created by the use of mathematics. He advocated that students should realize the formatting power instead of being unquestioningly controlled by it. Frankenstein (1989), based on Freire's pedagogy, used a concept of CME to question facts that are taken for granted with mathematics and wanted to show that the use of mathematics can by no means be considered neutral. Based on these ideas, many other projects were developed, which use the content in mathematics lessons in a critical manner to point out social injustices and actively counteract them (Gutstein, 2006), link culture and mathematics (e.g., D'Ambrosio, 1985; Powell & Frankenstein, 1997) or offer different perspectives on climate change (e.g., Coles et al., 2013). Although there have been great movements towards a form of mathematics education that

² I am aware that this does not mean that young people will not become actively involved later on without this kind of education. However, first, letting them deal with these democratic principles and societal topics already in school, can make it much easier for them to recognize personally important issues later, and second, it might pave the way for students who would otherwise not get the idea of becoming actively involved.

Why (mathematics) education in a democracy must be critical education

integrates critical aspects, it still appears to be exceptional in everyday teaching than a matter of course (at least within German-speaking countries). The fact that one does rather think of incorporating critical aspects within other subjects than mathematics, such as political education, geography, or history, might be due to specific characteristics of the subject:

First, more than any other science, mathematics is considered neutral and objective – a description of reality free of interpretation. Mathematics and numbers suggest universality and indisputability and make facts seem impersonal and neutral. With this attribution, it seems almost absurd to critically question mathematical facts (i.e., to look at contents in class also with regard to interest and benefit) or even to critically examine social events (which may also be represented by numbers) through mathematical glasses. If we encounter numbers in any theme, be it at school, in our private lives, or in the media, we quickly get the feeling that we are presented with unquestionable facts – one would have much less of an idea to criticize them than to criticize a verbal statement that says the same thing without numbers. This still powerful myth makes it tedious to establish critical education as a guiding principle in mathematics classes. However, it is precisely because it is easier to be convinced of numbers without critically reflecting on them that critical mathematics education is essential. That a blind trust in numbers is quite problematic within democratic societies, as numbers are often used to justify regulations, is shown in Porter (1996):

A decision made by the numbers [...] has at least the appearance of being fair and impersonal. Scientific objectivity thus provides an answer to a moral demand for impartiality and fairness. Quantification is a way of making decisions without seeming to decide. (p. 8)

What makes critical (mathematics) education even more important is the fact that we have now mutated into an ‘information society’ in which it is easy to access information from all over the world in real-time, and we are constantly surrounded by them. Hence, it has become more and more challenging to know which information is to trust. De kerrsmaker and Roets (2017) pointed out that people do not easily adjust their judgments if they get to know that what they first believed in has been proven to be wrong. It is a matter of cognitive abilities like reasoning, problem-solving, or understanding how willing people are to rethink their views based on misleading information (and, of course, also a matter of will to put these abilities to use). Gordon (2018) argued that critical thinking is a key capacity to combat misinformation in the news and that education plays a key role in developing such critical skills. That it is essential to train such skills in mathematics as well is shown by Willingham (2007) who stated that critical thinking could not function if there is no appropriate expertise in the background – which he called the domain knowledge. So, if we want students to understand and question, for example, whether the numbers presented in a political debate can be correct and what purpose they might serve, mathematical knowledge must also be present in the background (here, for example, interpreting graphics, handling large numbers, a basic understanding of mathematical models, ...). On the other hand, pure mathematical knowledge is not enough either – the critical examination of where, why, and how mathematical representations are used has to be trained too to be applied in

different situations: ‘Just as it makes no sense to try to teach factual content without giving students opportunities to practice using it, it also makes no sense to try to teach critical thinking devoid of factual content’ (p. 10). That is another reason why teaching only specialist knowledge in each subject is not sufficient.

This brings us to the second unique characteristic of mathematics education: no other subject than mathematics can do without any reference to social matters and worldly topics – these are usually even included in the curriculum. Geography deals with processes of globalization, languages require an essay on a socially relevant topic, or biology discusses diseases of affluence. However, in mathematics, teachers could focus on teaching mathematical rules and procedures without embedding them in non-mathematical contexts (and they did in specific times and places). An explicit reference to extra-curricular themes is really necessary only for very few fields of (school) mathematics (an exception would be financial mathematics). Of course, this does not mean that extra-school contexts automatically lead to critical education, but this at least provides a basis from which to start. It is also not enough to include real contexts into the classroom through dressed-up word problems that are supposed to help understand mathematics better but usually distort reality very broadly. Kühnel (1950), in his demand for a new way of arithmetic teaching, already pointed out that such an instruction can never fulfill higher educational goals:

Arithmetic must no longer remain and end in itself but should become a means to pursue higher purposes. The higher purposes, however, can be no other than the grasping of reality, which confronts us in spirit and nature, and the promotion of culture [...]. The purpose of arithmetic is to provide the basis for a mathematical understanding of the things and phenomena of nature and human life. (pp. 67–69, own translation)

Especially when time is short and the pressure to get students through standardized exams is high, these higher educational goals are pushed into the background – mathematics lessons get along wonderfully without including them. A development towards a critical education, especially in mathematics teaching, is a great challenge and probably requires a rethinking that starts at the institutional level so that overall conditions are created in which teachers can act accordingly.

These demands are not really new, and it may seem that they are self-evident demands on a school system in a democratic country. However, it is apparent that in the past, in many areas within education, nothing appropriate has happened to meet these demands in the long term. Furthermore, the developments of the last few years (or even of the last decade) indicate that the educational focus is on entirely different aspects than enhancing critical education and democratic values. The growing importance and spread of standardized tests in schools show their effects directly in the classroom. Pupils’ achievement is primarily measured only in their success on these tests, as they often serve as the key to higher education. Developments in the national school systems are initiated based on these standardized test results (e.g., A-level exams, PISA). In Austria, for instance, test performances are compared on a national level and schools that scored poorly are given a mandatory mandate by the school ministry to work with outside teams to develop the school so that a better

result is achieved on the next test. What happens is obvious: The focus in the classroom is on preparing students in the best possible way so that they perform well on these tests. Hence, what skills students actually evolve during their time in school (which is up to 13 years) gets less important than achieving high scores. Therefore, both teachers' and students' focus and source of pressure are clear – providing or getting the knowledge to pass these tests. Developing other skills will take a back seat and can be seen as an addition if there is some time left. Others have pointed out this problem as well. For example, White and Cooper (2015) demanded that 'instead of a system of education that valorizes test scores over authentic knowledge, what is needed is a system of education where student [sic] are free to explore, to investigate, to think and learn; in short, to become "critical thinkers"' (p. 17).

These developments show that the requirement of critical (mathematics) education is by no means outdated or something that can be taken for granted. Especially now, when we are constantly surrounded by information and, due to the strong global connections, events somewhere around the world can also have a direct impact on processes in our own country, it is more important than ever for our youth to develop a critical competence. Therefore, we as educators must not tire of positioning this as a central educational goal where everyone within the educational system needs to participate regardless of the subject. For, in the end, the most central aspect of a democracy is the informed citizen.

References

- Aguilar, M. S., & Zavaleta, J. G. M. (2012). On the links between mathematics education and democracy: A literature review. *Pythagoras*, 33(2), Article 164.
- Coles, A., Barwell, R., Cotton, T., Winter, J., & Brown, L. (2013). *Teaching secondary mathematics as if the planet matters*. Taylor & Francis.
- D'Ambrosio, U. (1985). Ethnomathematics and its place in the history and pedagogy of mathematics. *For the Learning of Mathematics*, 5(1), 44–48.
- De keersmaecker, J., & Roets, A. (2017). 'Fake news': Incorrect, but hard to correct. The role of cognitive ability on the impact of false information on social impressions. *Intelligence*, 65, 107–110.
- Dewey, J. (1997). *Democracy and education: An introduction to the philosophy of education*. Free Press. (Original work published 1916)
- Frankenstein, M. (1989). *Relearning mathematics: A different third R-radical math*. Free Association.
- Freire, P. (2014). *Pedagogy of the Oppressed*. Bloomsbury. (Original work published 1970)
- Giroux, H. A., & McLaren, P. (1989). Introduction: Schooling, cultural politics, and the struggle for democracy. In H. A. Giroux & P. McLaren (Eds.), *Teacher empowerment and school reform. Critical pedagogy, the state, and cultural struggle* (pp. xi–xxxv). State University of New York Press.
- Gordon, M. (2018). Lying in politics: Fake news, alternative facts, and the challenges for deliberative civics education. *Educational Theory*, 68(1), 49–64.
- Gutstein, E. (2006). *Reading and writing the world with mathematics: Toward a pedagogy for social justice*. Routledge.
- Hytten, K. (2008). Education for critical democracy and compassionate globalization. *Philosophy of Education Archive*, 333–341.

D. Steflitsch

- Klafki, W. (2007). *Neue Studien zur Bildungstheorie und Didaktik: Zeitgemäße Allgemeinbildung und kritisch-konstruktive Didaktik* [New studies in educational theory and didactics: Timely general education and critical-constructive didactics]. Beltz.
- Kühnel, J. (1924). *Die alte Schule* [The old school]. Klinkhardt.
- Kühnel, J. (1950). *Neubau des Rechenunterrichts* [New construction of arithmetic instruction]. Turm. (Original work published 1916)
- Oxford University Press. (2020). *critical*. <https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/critical>
- Porter, T. M. (1996). *Trust in numbers: The pursuit of objectivity in science and public life*. Princeton University Press.
- Powell, A. B., & Frankenstein, M. (1997). *Ethnomathematics: Challenging eurocentrism in mathematics education*. State University of New York Press.
- Skovsmose, O. (1985). Mathematical education versus critical education. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 16(4), 337–354.
- Skovsmose, O. (1994). *Towards a philosophy of critical mathematics education*. Kluwer.
- West, C. (2005). *Democracy matters: Winning the fight against imperialism*. Penguin.
- White, R. E., & Cooper, K. (2015). *Democracy and its discontents: Critical literacy across global contexts*. Sense.
- Willingham, D. (2007). Critical thinking: Why is it so hard to teach? *American Educator*, (15), 8–19.